

Knowledge Utilisation in Teaching Effectiveness among Lecturers in Library Schools in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of knowledge utilisation practices on the teaching effectiveness of lecturers in library schools across Southwest Nigeria. Teaching effectiveness is pivotal to achieving educational objectives, fostering critical thinking, and equipping students with the skills needed for societal progress. However, challenges such as inadequate integration of knowledge utilisation practices, limited adoption of innovative teaching methods, and insufficient institutional support have hindered teaching effectiveness in Nigerian library schools. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, involving 159 lecturers from 17 library schools across the region. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to explore lecturers'

knowledge utilisation practices and their impact on instructional delivery. Descriptive and inferential statistical tools, including regression analysis, were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that knowledge utilisation practices significantly influence teaching effectiveness. Lecturers who effectively applied knowledge through research, collaboration, and innovative classroom practices demonstrated higher teaching effectiveness. However, barriers such as insufficient resources, limited professional development opportunities, and inadequate infrastructure were identified as constraints to optimal knowledge utilisation. The study concludes that integrating robust knowledge utilisation practices into teaching frameworks is critical for enhancing teaching effectiveness and improving the quality of graduates produced by library schools. Recommendations include increased investment in faculty training, provision of state-of-the-art resources, and the development of policies that encourage knowledge sharing and utilisation among lecturers.

Keywords: Knowledge Utilisation, Teaching Effectiveness, Library Schools, Nigeria, Education.

Introduction

Teaching effectiveness can be described as the degree to which the learning outcome of teaching-learning processes of the educational system of a nation is achieved and the extent to which targeted educational problems are solved. Campbell et al. (2004), as cited in Ka Yuk Chan and Chen (2024), conceptualised teaching effectiveness as the degree to which instructional practices, teacher expectations, classroom organisation, and the use of learning resources

influence student performance. More recently, Zabeli (2024) emphasised that effective teaching extends beyond academic achievement to also foster students' emotional, psychological, and behavioral development through intentional and well-structured pedagogical approaches. Ka Yuk Chan and Chen (2024) conceptualised teaching effectiveness as a multifaceted construct that includes educators' inherent traits, professional capacity, instructional conduct, students' learning experiences and outcomes, training, institutional context, and learner characteristics. Additionally, Mejía-Rodríguez and Kyriakides (2022) highlighted the significance of system-level factors like financial resources, time allocation, teacher qualifications, and policy frameworks in shaping student learning outcomes, thereby broadening the scope of teaching effectiveness beyond just classroom and individual characteristics.

Although teaching effectiveness measures education systems' structure, processes, and learning outcomes, it depends on how well a society, institution, or individual lecturer achieves success in educational outcomes or how individual students' learning outcomes are achieved. It is the evaluation of everything that is directly or indirectly used for instructional delivery to facilitate or encourage the acquisition of knowledge, competence, skills, and know-how of students. Using the teaching effectiveness scale as a tool will enable instructors/lecturers to identify strengths as well as weaknesses and consider appropriate strategies to improve instruction where necessary (Mastrokoulou et al., 2022). Apart from improving instructional delivery, it increases stakeholders' satisfaction with learning outcomes and educational objectives set out in the curriculum.

The rationale of teaching effectiveness in library schools is to impart relevant job and soft skills knowledge to students who would become responsible future citizens, effective policy makers, and vectors of change. The significance of teaching effectiveness goes far beyond the goal of ameliorating the comprehension of the fundamental ethics of teaching by generating new knowledge that will expose students to real-life learning environments and ensure lifelong learning experiences. Teaching effectiveness implies that lecturers make the most significant impact on the lives of students, along with the expectations of society. Having long years of experience as a lecturer in the library school does not guarantee teaching effectiveness, as experience is useful only when the lecturer continually engages in self-reflection, professional development, and modifies

classroom techniques to better serve the needs of the students.

Lecturers must prepare to teach a range of students in terms of interests, motivation, ability, and students needing additional assistance. In addition, lecturers must strive to teach to accomplish educational objectives, make significant contributions to research, while maintaining quality and educational teaching effectiveness. Aldrup et al. (2022) presented indicators of teaching effectiveness as including adequacy of the course materials, teaching methodology of the lecturers, human relations of the subject lecturers, expertise of the lecturers, lecturers' punctuality at class, class environment, competency of the subject lecturers, and management and control in the class. Ka Yuk Chan and Chen (2024) also described these indicators as classroom practices like teaching methods, lecturers' expectations, classroom organisation, and the use of classroom resources. Classroom resources are a collection of teaching or instructional materials (animate, inanimate, human, or non-human) and supplies lecturers use while teaching and learning to assist or develop the desired objectives of students. This encompasses the print, such as textbooks, study guides, etc, audio (cassettes, podcasts, and so on), visual (charts, photographs, etc), audiovisual (slides, multimedia, etc) and electronic (computers, tablets, and so on) resources lecturers use to implement and facilitate the achievement of content taught to students. These resources make learning experiences more interesting, exciting, and interactive; and invariably concretise learning and assessment (Inegbedion, 2024). Arumuru and David (2024) confirmed that the instructional resources improved the learning achievements of students. Lecturers of library schools are expected to provide these resources, which, when used effectively by lecturers, would translate into improved teaching effectiveness and quality graduates.

Library schools in Nigeria, similar to higher education institutions worldwide, face numerous challenges that hinder their ability to fully achieve their objectives while also sustaining their traditional mandate of contributing meaningfully to societal development. Some of these challenges include failure of the government to fund education generally and library schools in particular, lack of effective mechanisms to combine diverse skills, knowledge, and expertise in the Nigerian education industry, growing demand for enrollment into higher institutions, increasing decay in infrastructural facilities and learning resources, as

well as deficiency of faculty members, especially those with doctoral degrees. Others are incessant strikes by lecturers in tertiary institutions; inadequate supervision of students, and poor knowledge management practices have further crippled library schools in Nigeria.

Nonetheless, an important concern in the nation's higher education sector is lack of national framework for measurement of teaching effectiveness, lack of national framework for integration of digital, electronic information and social media technologies and knowledge management practices into teaching and learning processes which have created a vacuum in the education sector for times immemorial thus making it possible for poor quality education leading to production of unemployable graduates. To this end, the knowledge management practice of knowledge utilisation is presumed to have an influence on the teaching effectiveness of lecturers, especially those in library schools.

Knowledge utilisation is the last component of the knowledge cycle in the management of knowledge. It is the process where individuals deliberately adapt validated information or knowledge for use to make necessary changes in their behaviour or practice. Knowledge utilisation is crucial to teaching effectiveness in higher education institutions. Minogue et al. (2022) defines knowledge utilisation as the intentional use of knowledge developed, refined, and disseminated by researchers and subsequently adapted by end users to meet specific objectives. More recently, Rickinson et al. (2022) introduced the Quality Use of Research Evidence (QURE) framework, emphasizing that effective knowledge utilisation in education hinges not only on engaging with robust research but also on the presence of supportive individual mindsets, organizational culture, infrastructure, and leadership to translate evidence into action. Lecturers as users of knowledge in library school need appropriate application of research-generated information/knowledge or innovation to enhance lesson plans, teaching-learning processes, research productivity and lecture delivery to students so as to improve students' learning outcomes, such as teaching effectiveness, students' academic performance, and students' self-efficacy, and so on.

A knowledge utilisation practice is based on the principle of partnership, collaboration, cooperation and shared or collective decision making between the communities of researchers and lecturers/policy-makers (Daza et al., 2021). Partnership refers to the process of establishing a social mutual relationship among communities of researchers, communities of

lecturers, administrators, policy-makers, and student groups on the value of research in the teaching profession. Collaboration occurs when each of the communities of researchers and lecturers is aware, adapts, and utilises validated knowledge, expertise or capabilities obtained through research in a student manner to achieve predetermined educational goals. Collaboration builds the unity, security and confidence needed to handle demanding lecturing tasks (Brain et al., 2022). Collective decision-making refers to shared process expertise between the communities of researchers and lecturers to execute processes in a consistent manner, for optimal resource efficiency, cost effectiveness, service delivery and community services while cooperation refers to the process of having a common theme establishing a mutual understanding of research between the two communities of researchers and lecturers so that they can better communicate with each other.

Higher educational institutions, mostly universities play a significant role in promoting knowledge utilisation in the advancement of teaching profession with a view to improve lecturers' involvement in research activities. Lecturers' involvement in research activities can enhance lecturers' understanding and appreciation of the practical value of research and equip them with necessary knowledge and skills to consume research findings, interpret and conduct research to solve problems at work and be more innovative in instructional delivery. Such involvement, that is, the symbiotic relationship between the two communities of researchers and lecturers can nurture a culture of research in lecturers and make them to consume research findings and also initiate research. Sukarno and Riyadini (2024) affirmed that research serves to create new knowledge, contribute to the growth of teaching-learning processes, improve problem-solving and decision making in the work place, make lecturers critical consumers of the research literature, and equip lecturers to provide quality teaching and improve instructional delivery to students. Knowledge utilisation manifests in the daily routine of job related activities of lecturers (Roman-Liu et al., 2025). However, if knowledge utilisation is effectively practiced among lecturers, it will reduce duplication of efforts; serve as basis for solving problems at the faculty, and the institution at large and enhance decision-making processes. Knowledge utilisation in higher education is a way of making a learning institution more competitive.

The origin of library education in Nigeria dates back to 1959, when the University College Ibadan (now

the University of Ibadan) introduced a Postgraduate Diploma in Librarianship to expand access to formal training in the profession. This initiative, supported by funding from the Carnegie Corporation of New York, was influenced by Lancour's recommendations to establish a postgraduate-level library school, which led to the creation of the Institute of Librarianship, currently the Department of Library, Archival and Information Studies. The second library school was founded in 1965 at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, offering an undergraduate programme in response to F. A. Sharr's 1963 report on library needs in Northern Nigeria, thereby complementing the postgraduate training model at Ibadan (Ibrahim, 2004). Over the past two decades, the landscape of library education in Nigeria has expanded significantly. By 2020, there were 37 library schools across federal, state, and private universities, alongside emerging programmes in polytechnics and colleges (Khallaf et al., 2022). Of these, 13 are located in the South-West geopolitical zone, which informed the focus of this study.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching effectiveness is pivotal to the quality of education, the structure and processes of academic institutions, and the learning outcomes of students. However, studies have reported low to moderate levels of teaching effectiveness among lecturers in Nigeria, particularly in library schools. This is evident in the declining quality of graduates produced by these institutions. Preliminary findings indicate significant challenges, including irregular class attendance by lecturers, inadequate pedagogical methods, and a lack of mastery in delivering course content. These issues are exacerbated by limited access to appropriate teaching resources, ultimately resulting in poor student performance and negatively impacting the ranking of universities.

An essential aspect of teaching effectiveness is the ability of lecturers to utilise knowledge effectively in their instructional practices. Knowledge utilisation encompasses the application of acquired insights, skills, and innovations to enhance teaching, improve student learning outcomes, and address emerging challenges in the academic environment. However, evidence suggests that lecturers in Nigerian library schools have not fully embraced knowledge utilisation practices. Many fail to incorporate new teaching strategies, research findings, and technological innovations into their classroom delivery. This lack of emphasis on knowledge utilisation

limits their ability to adapt to the constantly evolving educational landscape and impedes their capacity to meet the demands of 21st-century education.

In addition, the absence of institutional frameworks that encourage knowledge utilisation practices further exacerbates this issue. While conferences, workshops, and professional training opportunities are available, their impact remains minimal due to inadequate follow-through and the reluctance of lecturers to implement what they learn. Consequently, library schools struggle to keep pace with global educational trends, particularly in adopting technology-driven teaching methods and leveraging social media and other ICT tools to improve learning outcomes.

Currently, little is known about the extent to which knowledge utilisation practices influence the teaching effectiveness of lecturers in Nigerian library schools. This gap highlights the need for an in-depth investigation into the role of knowledge utilisation in enhancing teaching effectiveness.

The study was aimed at exploring the influence of knowledge utilisation practices on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest Nigeria. The findings provide insights into the importance of knowledge utilisation and offer recommendations to improve teaching standards in library schools and the broader educational system.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of knowledge utilisation on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in the Southwest, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the knowledge utilisation practices among lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria;
- ii. Ascertain the level of teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in the southwest, Nigeria;
- iii. To determine the influence of knowledge utilisation practices on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in southwest, Nigeria

Research questions

The following research questions will guide the conduct of this study:

- i. What constitutes the knowledge utilisation practices among lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the level of teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Research hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance:

Ho1: Knowledge utilisation practices have no significant influence on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in the southwest, Nigeria.

Literature review

Concept of Knowledge Utilisation Practices

Knowledge utilisation, which serves as a crucial link between theory and practice, refers to the deliberate application of validated knowledge to achieve specific objectives or solve problems. It represents the final phase of the knowledge management cycle, emphasizing the movement of knowledge from generation and dissemination to practical implementation (Minogue et al., 2022). Rather than implying an immediate and direct impact, knowledge utilisation is a gradual, iterative process shaped by continuous interaction between researchers, educators, and policymakers (Ifenthaler et al., 2021). Ifenthaler et al. (2021) model outlines seven stages, they are: reception, cognition, reference, effort, adoption, implementation, and impact. This model offers a framework for understanding how knowledge influences decision-making and practice over time.

However, knowledge utilisation is influenced by various systemic barriers, which Ifenthaler et al. (2021) categorizes into three routes: the supply side (e.g., lack of relevant research, inequitable access, poor communication of findings), the demand side (e.g., limited awareness, resource constraints, selective use of evidence), and the context side (e.g., weak connections between researchers and practitioners, domain-specific limitations, and contested knowledge validity). Overcoming these barriers requires strong engagement between knowledge creators and end-users, with shared responsibility for adapting and applying insights in practical settings (Verville et al., 2021). Notwithstanding the barriers, knowledge utilisation involves several phases as reported by Tukisi et al. (2025):

1. Knowledge Acquisition: Identifying, collecting, and recognizing valuable knowledge from various sources such as research, literature reviews, and industry benchmarks. Effective acquisition requires a robust organizational knowledge management system to avoid underutilisation of valuable

information (Tukisi et al., 2025).

2. Knowledge Documentation: Converting tacit or experiential knowledge into transferable formats, such as written, graphical, or digital media. This step often faces challenges due to time constraints and outdated documentation practices, highlighting the need for technology-driven solutions (Tukisi et al., 2025).
3. Transmission and Access: Making documented knowledge widely accessible to intended users while maintaining contextual linkages. Access can be targeted (direct delivery to users) or open (broad availability through repositories and platforms).
4. Perception and Learning: Users interpret and internalize knowledge, integrating it into their own mental frameworks. The extent of understanding determines the effectiveness of subsequent application.
5. Decision-Making and Action: The final phase involves using knowledge to inform decisions, strategies, or innovations. This often requires multi-criteria analysis, balancing knowledge relevance, organizational priorities, and contextual realities.

These stages highlight that knowledge utilisation is not a passive activity but a dynamic, continuous process that underpins effective decision-making and instructional innovation.

Knowledge Utilisation Practices and Teaching Effectiveness

Utilisation can be described as the strategic application of tangible or intangible knowledge resources to achieve specific outcomes (Walshaw, 2012). Within the scope of this study, knowledge utilisation refers to the extent to which lecturers in Library and Information Science (LIS) settings draw upon research-based knowledge to inform instructional practices and improve teaching outcomes. This conceptualisation focuses on evidence derived from scholarly research rather than personal or experiential knowledge shared among colleagues or teacher-researchers (Al-Rasheed and Berri, 2017). It involves a deliberate process of locating, evaluating, interpreting, and translating academic findings into actionable strategies for classroom application.

Lin and Chen (2006) define knowledge utilisation as the ability to operationalise knowledge in an environment that fosters collaboration, experimentation, and innovation. Similarly, Ottoson (2009) highlights

that applying knowledge is fundamental to evaluating and adopting new insights, particularly in academic environments where knowledge directly influences research productivity and instructional performance. Importantly, knowledge needs and utilisation vary according to user type; studies by Chapman et al. (2021) demonstrate that practitioners, administrators, and policymakers require different approaches, communication channels, and formats for knowledge application.

Given its critical role in enhancing educational quality, the integration of research evidence into teaching practices has become increasingly necessary, particularly in the face of rising student populations and evolving curriculum demands. However, despite its advantages, knowledge utilisation remains underdeveloped in Nigerian tertiary institutions. du Toit and van Petegem (2005) observed that limited awareness and insufficient institutional support restrict lecturers from fully adopting research-driven teaching strategies. Nevenglosky (2018) similarly identified inadequate lecturer engagement with innovative practices as a barrier to effective curriculum implementation, while DaRosa et al. (2011) pointed to weak researcher–lecturer collaboration as a major factor impeding the application of knowledge in teaching contexts.

More recent scholarship confirms these challenges, emphasizing the need for system-wide interventions that promote evidence-based teaching. For instance, Rickinson et al. (2022) argue that effective knowledge use in education depends on leadership commitment, organisational infrastructure, and a culture of continuous learning. This underscores the importance of strengthening both individual and institutional capacity to translate research into practice within LIS education.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to systematically collect data and describe the characteristics and behaviours of the target population without influencing them. The population comprised all lecturers in Library and Information Science (LIS) programmes in Southwest Nigeria. A total of 159 lecturers from 17 institutions offering LIS programmes formed the study population, including private and public universities and polytechnics. Neither sample nor sampling technique was used, but total enumeration of the population involving all 159 lecturers, ensuring that the study captured comprehensive data as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Study Population.

S/N	Library Schools	Number of Lecturers
1	Oyo State Polytechnic, Eruwa, Oyo State	7
2	Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State	9
3	Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State	8
4	Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State	11
5	Babcock University, Illisan-Remo, Ogun State	12
6	Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State	11
7	University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State	18
8	Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State	14
9	Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State	7
10	Federal University, Oye, Ekiti State	12
11	Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State	9
12	Leeds City University, Ibadan, Oyo State	12
13	Bowen University, Iwo, Osun State	5
14	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State	7
15	Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Oyo State	4
16	Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State	4
17	The Polytechnic Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State	9
Total		159

Sources: Office of the HOD of each Institution; Field Survey, 2023

Methodology

Data Collection

Data collection was achieved using a structured

questionnaire titled “Social Media Use, Knowledge Creation, and Utilisation on Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire (SMU-KCU-TEQ).” The questionnaire was designed to elicit detailed responses on social

media use, knowledge practices, and teaching effectiveness, comprising eight sections:

- Section A focused on respondents’ demographic information, including age, gender, marital status, rank, and teaching experience.
- Sections B to H addressed various dimensions of the study, including the types and extent of social media usage, purposes for which social media tools are employed, knowledge creation and utilisation practices, elements of teaching effectiveness, and challenges affecting these domains.

The questionnaire utilised a 4-point Likert scale to measure responses, with modifications for specific items. Adaptation from prior validated scales ensured relevance and reliability.

Instrument Reliability

Reliability testing was conducted on a sample of 10 lecturers each from three institutions outside the study area (University of Ilorin, Kwara State University, and Federal Polytechnic Offa). The paired scores from a two-week interval test were analyzed using Cronbach’s Alpha via SPSS (version 23.0). Results demonstrated high reliability across all sections, with coefficients exceeding the 0.7 threshold (e.g., 0.961 for the extent of social media

use and 0.881 for knowledge utilisation practices).

Response Rate

Out of 159 questionnaires distributed, 141 were returned, yielding an impressive 88.67% response rate. This high rate underscores the effectiveness of the data collection process and the respondents’ engagement.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed:

- Descriptive statistics (e.g., frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations) summarized demographic data and responses to research questions.
- Inferential statistics, particularly regression analysis, tested the study’s hypotheses to explore relationships between variables such as knowledge utilisation practices and teaching effectiveness. All analyses were conducted using SPSS version 23.0.

Results

Research Question 1: What constitutes the knowledge utilisation practices among lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Lecturers’ Knowledge Utilisation Practices.

Items	SA N(%)	A N(%)	D N(%)	SD N(%)	Mean	SD
Knowledge utilisation practices empower my learning-teaching skills	104(73.8)	37(26.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.74	0.44
I utilise knowledge through collaboration with research institutes and other institutions (such as industries, marketplaces, etc.)	103(73.0)	38(27.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.73	0.45
Knowledge utilisation practices help me to acquire series of ideas to promote students’ learning	99(70.2)	42(29.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.70	0.46
I utilise knowledge through research and development initiatives	96(68.1)	45(31.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.68	0.47
Knowledge utilisation practices help me manage my instructional time and delivery appropriately	108(76.6)	20(14.2)	13(9.2)	0(0.0)	3.67	0.64
Knowledge utilisation practices enhance my innovative ideas of handling students in classroom interactions.	91(64.5)	50(35.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.65	0.48
My involvement in academic seminars, workshops, and conferences assists me to cross-fertilising positive ideas	89(63.1)	52(36.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.63	0.48
Knowledge utilisation practices assist me in proper planning and delivery of classroom instructions	95(67.4)	33(23.4)	13(9.2)	0(0.0)	3.58	0.66
Knowledge utilisation practices equip me with the right skills needed for transfer of knowledge to students	81(57.4)	60(42.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.57	0.50
I utilise knowledge through collaboration with other lecturers and researchers within and outside my department and the university	67(47.5)	74(52.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.48	0.50
Average Mean					3.64	0.51
Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree						
Degree ***Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.99 = Low; 2.00 to 2.99 = Moderate; 3.00 to 3.99 = High; (%) = Frequency (percentage)						

Table 2 revealed a high level of knowledge utilisation practices among the Lecturers in the selected

library schools, with an overall average mean of 3.64 on the scale of 4points. It shows that the items with the

highest score were knowledge utilisation practices that empower my learning-teaching skills (mean = 3.74) followed by utilising knowledge through collaboration with research institutes and other institutions (mean = 3.73). Others include knowledge utilisation practices help me to acquire series of ideas to promote students’ learning (mean = 3.70), utilise knowledge through research and development initiatives (mean = 3.68), knowledge utilisation practices help me manage my instructional time and delivery appropriately (mean = 3.67), Knowledge utilisation practices enhance my innovative ideas of handling students in classroom interactions (mean = 3.65), My involvement in academic seminars, workshops and conferences assists me to cross-fertilise positive ideas (mean = 3.63), Knowledge utilisation practices assist me in proper planning and

delivery of classroom instructions (mean = 3.58), Knowledge utilisation practices equip me with the right skills needed for transfer of knowledge to students (mean = 3.57), utilise knowledge through collaboration with other lecturers and researchers within and outside my department and the university (mean = 3.48). The average mean score of 3.64 reflects a strong application of knowledge utilisation practices, demonstrating their critical role in improving teaching effectiveness, fostering innovation, and enhancing collaborative efforts. These practices underscore the importance of continuous learning and external engagement in the academic environment.

Research Question 2: What is the level of teaching effectiveness of lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Lecturers’ Level of Teaching Effectiveness.

ITEMS	SA N(%)	A N(%)	D N(%)	SD N(%)	Mean	SD
As a lecturer, I :						
Am reasonably obedient and loyal to my head of the department for achievement of the departmental goals	131(92.9)	10(7.1)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.93	0.26
Give instant response to feedbacks given by my students to motivate them to learn effectively.	113(80.1)	28(19.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.80	0.40
The test I intend administering to my students will be reviewed and improved upon by me in line with expected learning objectives.	112(79.4)	29(20.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.79	0.41
Organise the subject matter I teach to be in agreement with the curriculum and courses’ objectives to improve my students’ capacity to learn	108(76.6)	33(23.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.77	0.43
Have confidence that the quality of my interaction and instruction can contribute effectively to my students learning.	100(70.9)	41(29.1)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.71	0.46
Provide a lot of activities and examples aimed at developing critical thinking skills among my students.	109(77.3)	19(13.5)	13(9.2)	0(0.0)	3.68	0.64
Get my students engaged with the 21 st century instructional aids and support to effectively maximise my students learning gains.	94(66.7)	47(33.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.67	0.47
Plan my lessons based on the curriculum and techniques tested and found suitable to attain educational objectives	94(66.7)	47(33.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.67	0.47
Guide my students in completing their assignments towards achieving learning objectives and improving academic performance.	94(66.7)	47(33.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.67	0.47
Encourage my students to ask questions in order to evaluate their understanding of the lessons taught.	93(66.0)	48(34.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.66	0.48
Belief that having adequate content knowledge can contribute to overall stated objective of learning.	90(63.8)	51(36.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.64	0.48
Consider my first duty is to be devoted to getting competitive advantage and a good name to my school	90(63.8)	51(36.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.64	0.48
Display friendly attitude towards my students in order to motivate them to learn effectively.	90(63.8)	51(36.2)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.64	0.48
Take into consideration my students’ moral and social development in lessons taught for lifelong learning.	103(73.0)	25(17.7)	13(9.2)	0(0.0)	3.64	0.65
Ask, while teaching, more thought provoking questions than fact finding questions to improve instructional effectiveness towards my students.	89(63.1)	52(36.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.63	0.48
In the end I am in the habit of summarising the lessons taught, for sustainable academic achievement of my students.	95(67.4)	33(23.4)	13(9.2)	0(0.0)	3.58	0.66
Understand that setting of adequate instructional objectives before teaching can improve my students’ academic achievement	81(57.4)	60(42.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.57	0.50
Plan my lessons keeping in view the individual differences among my students to improve their academic performances	79(56.0)	62(44.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3.56	0.50
Observe flexibility of instructional delivery to be able to fit to the different academic needs of my students.	1(7)	60(42.6)	0(0.0)	80(56.7)	3.55	0.54
Do not discuss with students their performances in tests to improve their academic performance	35(24.8)	43(30.5)	10(7.1)	53(37.6)	2.43	1.23
Average Mean					3.61	0.53
Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly Disagree						
Degree ***Decision Rule if mean is ≤ 1.99 = Low; 2.00 to 2.99 = Moderate; 3.00 to 3.99 = High; (%) = Frequency (percentage)						

The data in Table 3 provide insight into the level of teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest Nigeria. The findings reveal the various dimensions of teaching practices

and their perceived effectiveness based on lecturers’ responses.

The lecturers exhibited the highest level of agreement in being obedient and loyal to their

department heads to achieve departmental goals, with a mean score of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 0.26, reflecting a strong commitment to institutional objectives. Similarly, giving instant responses to student feedback to motivate effective learning scored a mean of 3.80, indicating widespread adoption of responsive teaching practices.

Reviewing and improving test materials to align with learning objectives scored a mean of 3.79, suggesting lecturers prioritize alignment with educational goals. Organizing subject matter in accordance with curriculum objectives scored 3.77, while confidence in the quality of instruction contributing to student learning achieved a mean of 3.71, indicating a strong emphasis on quality teaching practices.

Activities and examples aimed at fostering critical thinking skills among students received a mean score of 3.68, demonstrating the lecturers' focus on higher-order cognitive skills. Utilizing 21st-century instructional aids and planning lessons based on proven techniques scored 3.67, showing a dedication to modern and evidence-based teaching methods.

Guiding students in assignments, encouraging questioning, and integrating moral and social development into lessons were all rated highly,

with mean scores above 3.60, emphasizing holistic and student-centered instructional approaches. The belief in the role of content knowledge in achieving learning objectives and fostering a friendly learning environment also scored 3.64, highlighting the importance of subject mastery and positive student-teacher relationships.

Lower-rated practices included summarizing lessons (3.58) and planning lessons based on individual differences (3.56). However, the lowest-rated item was discussing test performance with students, which received a mean of 2.43, indicating moderate application and possible areas for improvement in feedback practices.

The overall average mean score of 3.61 demonstrates a high level of teaching effectiveness, with lecturers emphasizing responsive, collaborative, and innovative teaching practices that align with curriculum goals and student learning needs. This highlights a commitment to quality teaching and a need for enhanced focus on individualized learning and performance discussions.

H01: Knowledge utilisation practices have no significant influence on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of the Significant Influence of Knowledge Utilisation Practices on Teaching Effectiveness among Lecturers in Library Schools in the Southwest, Nigeria.

R Square	0.947	Df	140
Adjusted R Square	0.946	Mean Square	5242.013; 2.131
Std. Error of the regression Estimate	1.460	F statistics	2460.194
Sum of Squares	5538.184	Prob. (F statistics)	0.000

The regression analysis results in Table 4 evaluate the influence of knowledge utilisation practices on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest Nigeria. The findings show that the R Square value of 0.947 indicates that 94.7% of the variance in teaching effectiveness is explained by knowledge utilisation practices. This high value demonstrates the strong predictive power of these practices. Adjusted R Square, at 0.946, confirms the robustness of the model, accounting for the number of predictors included. The standard error of the regression estimate, 1.460, shows minimal deviation of observed values from the predicted values, indicating a well-fitted model. The F-statistic value of 2460.194 underscores the statistical significance of the model, supported by a p-value of 0.000, which confirms a strong relationship between knowledge utilisation practices and teaching effectiveness.

The mean square for the regression, 5242.013, is significantly larger than the residual mean square of 2.131, further affirming the model's ability to explain the variance in teaching effectiveness. The total sum of squares, 5538.184, reflects the overall variance in the data, with the majority being accounted for by the model. These results lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H01) that knowledge utilisation practices have no significant influence on teaching effectiveness. Instead, the findings highlight the critical role of knowledge utilisation practices in enhancing teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in the southwest, Nigeria.

Discussion

The finding showed that what constitutes the knowledge utilisation practices among lecturers in

library schools in the Southwest, Nigeria, was moderate. This suggests a foundation for effective knowledge application and dissemination. To further enhance these practices, lecturers can consider strategies such as balancing teaching and research, expanding knowledge dissemination, embracing collaboration and interdisciplinary engagement, and prioritizing ongoing professional development. These efforts can contribute to the advancement of the field and the overall quality of education in the region. The finding is in line with the finding of Tsoetsi and Onaolapo (2024) who reported that lecturers often balance teaching responsibilities with research endeavors. A moderate level of knowledge utilisation may indicate that lecturers are effectively integrating their research findings into their teaching activities. However, there may be opportunities for enhancing this integration. Osterling and Austin (2013) who submitted that effective knowledge utilisation involves disseminating research findings and insights to students, colleagues, and the broader academic community. Lecturers play a pivotal role in sharing their expertise and contributing to the scholarly discourse.

Moderate knowledge utilisation practices may suggest that lecturers are actively engaged in knowledge dissemination, but may explore additional avenues for sharing their work. Similarly, Tan (2016) reported that enhancing knowledge utilisation practices often involves collaborative efforts and interdisciplinary engagement. Lecturers can leverage collaboration with colleagues within and outside their discipline to broaden the impact of their research and teaching. Moderate utilisation practices may suggest that there is room to expand interdisciplinary collaboration. Lecturers can enhance their knowledge utilisation practices by continuously investing in professional development and lifelong learning. Staying updated with the latest research, pedagogical methods, and technological advancements can lead to more effective knowledge application.

The finding showed that knowledge utilisation practices have a significant influence on teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in South-West, Nigeria. This implies that lecturers who effectively apply their knowledge and expertise can provide students with a more engaging, practical, and relevant learning experience, ultimately contributing to improving teaching effectiveness in library schools in Southwest Nigeria. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Harbour et al. (2015) reported that lecturers who effectively utilise their knowledge in their teaching practices can provide students with practical insights and

real-world applications of the subject matter. This can enhance the relevance of the curriculum and improve students' understanding.

Knowledge utilisation practices often involve problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Lecturers who engage in such practices can encourage their students to think critically, analyze information, and apply their knowledge to solve complex problems. This contributes to improved teaching effectiveness (James et al., 2019). Similarly, Silver et al. (2019) remarked that lecturers who utilise their knowledge can innovate and implement effective pedagogical strategies in their teaching. They can adapt their approaches based on the latest research findings and emerging best practices, leading to more engaging and effective teaching methods. Knowledge utilisation often involves integrating research findings into teaching. Lecturers who engage in this practice can expose students to cutting-edge research, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Lecturers who effectively utilise knowledge are more likely to adapt their teaching methods based on feedback and assessment data. This continual improvement is essential for maintaining teaching effectiveness and meeting the evolving needs of students.

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical role of knowledge utilisation practices in enhancing teaching effectiveness among lecturers in library schools in Southwest Nigeria. The findings reveal that effective application of knowledge through research, collaboration, and innovative instructional practices significantly contributes to better learning outcomes and the production of highly skilled graduates. Lecturers who integrate these practices into their teaching demonstrate greater adaptability to the dynamic demands of 21st-century education.

However, several barriers, including insufficient resources, limited professional development opportunities, and inadequate institutional support, hinder the full adoption of knowledge utilisation practices. These challenges underscore the need for targeted interventions to bridge the gaps in knowledge application within the academic landscape of Nigerian library schools.

The study concludes that fostering a culture of knowledge utilisation is pivotal for improving teaching effectiveness. By prioritizing professional development, investing in modern teaching resources, and creating supportive policies, library schools can align with global educational standards. These efforts will not only enhance teaching practices but also contribute to the

broader goal of producing competent, innovative, and job-ready graduates who can drive societal progress.

Recommendations

To enhance teaching effectiveness in library schools, it is crucial to prioritize integrating knowledge utilisation practices into instructional frameworks. Institutions should invest in the professional development of lecturers by organizing workshops, seminars, and training sessions focused on innovative teaching strategies, knowledge sharing, and the use of modern educational technologies. Such programmes should emphasize practical applications to ensure lecturers can effectively translate theoretical insights into classroom practices.

Additionally, there is a need to provide adequate resources and infrastructure to support knowledge utilisation. This includes equipping library schools with state-of-the-art facilities, access to digital learning tools, and robust ICT systems that facilitate collaboration and innovation. Institutions should also develop clear policies and frameworks that encourage knowledge sharing among lecturers and promote interdisciplinary research collaborations.

Efforts should also be directed towards creating a supportive academic environment that recognizes and rewards effective knowledge utilisation. This can be achieved through mentorship programmes, peer support systems, and platforms that allow lecturers to exchange ideas and best practices. Furthermore, lecturers should be encouraged to engage with external stakeholders, such as industries and research institutes, to broaden their perspectives and incorporate real-world applications into their teaching.

By addressing these areas, library schools can significantly improve teaching effectiveness, align with global educational standards, and produce graduates with the skills and knowledge needed to excel in the modern workforce.

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